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Catalyst layer design with non-noble supports for ultra-low loaded anodic catalyst layers for PEM water electrolysis

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Abstract

Iridium scarcity is widely recognized as one of the main challenges for the mass commercialization of PEM electrolyzers [1], limiting it to a maximum loading of below 0.2 mg/cm² compared to the current standard of > 1 mg/cm². Reducing the iridium loading in the anodic catalyst layer leads to an increase in cell voltage. This has been attributed to the discontinuous nature of low loaded catalyst layers, which results in a considerable increase of the electric in-plane resistance [2]. One potential solution to this is addition of components other than IrO₂ nanoparticles between the catalyst and the porous transport layer resulting in state-of-the-art performance while also enabling a great reduction of iridium loading [3]. This study presents iridium and non-noble stable materials integrated within the catalyst layer and analyzes their effect on cell voltage, along with a deconvolution of kinetic, ohmic and mass transport overpotentials and ex-situ characterization.

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Introduction

The production of around 10 million tons of green hydrogen is targeted in the EU by 2030. To meet this demand, 40 GW of electrolysis capacity have to be installed by then. [1] A key technology to produce green hydrogen is PEM electrolysis (PEM = Proton Exchange Membrane) with its advantage of being capable to operate with fluctuating green electricity from e.g. wind or solar power. In a PEM electrolyzer, electrical energy is converted into chemical energy in the form of oxygen and hydrogen with high gas purity and high conversion efficiency. As PEM electrolyzers are operated in acidic conditions at relatively high potentials, the need of precious metal catalysts is one of the biggest challenges for PEM electrolysis upscaling. [2] Especially Iridium as catalyst for the oxygen evolution reaction is a critical, as this metal is one of the rarest ones on the planet. As the annual production volume of iridium is not sufficient to meet upscaling needs, novel concepts for recycling, catalyst synthesis and electrode design with the goal of reducing the noble metal loading in PEM electrolyzers have to be developed. Crucial for the approach of reducing the noble metal content is that while having significantly less catalyst material in the electrodes, performance and lifetime need to be maintained. According to Minke et al., a reduction in the loading of iridium from currently approximately 2 mg_{Ir}/cm² to 0.4 mg_{Ir}/cm² is necessary if the expansion rate for PEM electrolyzers in Germany is planned for 5 GW/year in 2050. [3]

One approach to develop high-performing, low iridium loaded PEM electrolysis cells is to support the few iridium nanoparticles in a low loaded anode electrode with nanofibers that act as interlayer between the titanium porous transport layer (PTL) at the anode side and the anode catalyst layer that is deposited on the membrane. In this regard, Hegge et al. reported a hybrid catalyst layer design with electrospun IrO₂-nanofibers deposited onto a low loaded iridium nanoparticle layer. [4] The nanofibers act as electrically conductive bridges between the otherwise electrically insulated catalyst particle islands in low loaded anodes (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Hybrid catalyst layer design for anodes in PEM electrolysis. Iridium nanoparticles in low loaded PEM electrolysis anode catalyst layers can be electrically insulated both in-plane and from the PTL (a and c). Introducing an iridium nanofiber layer between the iridium nanoparticle layer and the PTL improves the electrical contact between the catalyst layer and the PTL and it connects otherwise electrically insulated iridium particles (b and d). [4]

With the hybrid catalyst layer design an increase in mass activity of the iridium catalyst in low loaded anodes was demonstrated. The overall iridium loading could be reduced to 0.2 mg_{Ir}/cm² while keeping a similar performance as the 1.2 mg_{Ir}/cm² loaded reference cell in the standard iridium nanoparticle design (no fiber interlayer).

The presented hybrid design show great potential for improvement and further studies as explained in more detail in the section “Scientific Approach”.

Besides inventing new electrode designs with e.g. a layer by layer nanoparticle and nanofiber layer, catalysts can be directly supported by a carrier material to increase the active surface area, which allows for a significant reduction of the overall noble metal loading. Using supported catalysts is state of the art at the cathode side in PEM electrolyzers. For the hydrogen evolution reaction at the cathode, platinum supported on carbon is used and well-known as catalyst from fuel cells. Various carbon supports are available to meet different demands on performance and lifetime. For PEM electrolysis, carbon supports cannot be used at the anode side as support for iridium, as carbon corrodes at the high potentials being present.

Due to the harsh conditions in PEM electrolysis operation at the anode side, only a few materials are suitable as supports for the iridium catalyst. Transition metal oxides are considered as promising due to their stability in acidic media, relatively high electric conductivity and good interaction with a noble metal coating, potentially leading to an increased long-term stability. [5, 6]

In previous work, a core-shell design was presented with iridium being deposited on TiO₂ particles. [7] Figure 2 shows cross-sections of the unsupported IrO₂ based catalyst layer, the core-shell IrO₂@TiO₂ catalyst and a commercial TiO₂/IrO₂ catalyst. It could be demonstrated that by supporting the iridium catalyst in the core-shell design, not only the mass activity was improved during operation but that in addition, manufacturing steps as catalyst ink mixing were improved. The supported iridium catalyst showed significantly less sedimentation of the solid particles during and after ink mixing compared to the unsupported IrO₂ catalyst.

Figure 2: Cross-sections of anode catalyst layers with a) unsupported IrO₂ (Premion, AlfaAesar), b) in-house synthesized IrO₂@TiO₂ core-shell catalyst, c) commercial IrO₂/TiO₂ (Umicore) as supported iridium reference. [7]

Another transition metal oxide gaining more and more attention to serve as support for iridium catalyst in PEM electrolysis is antimony doped tin oxide (ATO). Compared to an unsupported iridium catalyst, a 75-fold reduction of the precious metal content when using IrO₂@ATO was demonstrated [8] as well as a 2.5-fold higher activity for the oxygen evolution reaction. [9] In PEM electrolysis full-cell tests, ATO-supported iridium reached a 40% reduction in IrO₂ content [10].

Besides the choice of material for the support, also the form of the supporting structure has an impact on the catalyst synthesis and the activity of the catalyst being deposited on the support during PEM electrolysis operation. In state of the art, particle powder supports are most common as well known from Pt/C supported catalysts or from core-shell designs. The fact that particle powders are commercially available in various material types and particle sizes, might be one simple reason for the wide use of particle supports compared to other forms as e.g. nanofibers.

The goal of this contribution is to motivate - based on previous work presented above - the use of different electrospun noble and non-noble nanofiber supports integrated in ultra-low loaded iridium anodes for PEM water electrolyzers showing i) the feasibility for upscaling ii) a high degree of reproducibility in fabrication and performance iii) in-situ testing up to high current densities.

1. Scientific Approach

From a scientific point of view the comparison between the following catalyst layer configurations are highly interesting to evaluate the influence of a supporting material (noble or non-noble) on the performance of a low loaded iridium based PEM electrolysis cell:

1. Iridium nanoparticles supported by a nanofiber layer (iridium-based nanofibers or non-noble metal fibers)
 - a. With the nanofibers acting as intermediate layer between the iridium nanoparticles deposited on the membrane and the titanium PTL (as in [4])
 - b. With the iridium nanoparticles mixed with the nanofiber support
2. Iridium deposited directly on particle or nanofiber supports.

Not only the influence on performance has to be studied but also the influence of integrating a support material (particle or nanofiber form) on different manufacturing steps when preparing the membrane electrode assembly (MEA):

1. Catalyst ink: When using a supported catalyst powder (iridium deposited on particle or nanofiber) the stability of the catalyst ink is expected to be improved compared to using an unsupported iridium catalyst. The choice of solvent system and improved ink stability will lead to more homogeneous preparation of catalyst layers and thus higher reproducibility in loading distribution and performance.
2. Catalyst layer: Supported iridium catalysts are expected to form homogeneous catalyst layer when e.g. being spray coated or casted. As result, loading distribution and performance should be more reproducible and damages of the cell e.g. by local hot spots should be reduced. It is also expected, that with a more stable catalyst ink and layer deposition, the thickness of catalyst layers can be reduced while maintaining a continuous catalyst particle distribution. The possibility to fabricate catalyst layers with ultra low thicknesses is mandatory on the way to reduce the overall catalyst loading in the PEM electrolysis cell.

To evaluate the influence of different catalyst supports for iridium either as additional supporting layer between the catalyst layer and the PTL or integrated in the catalyst layer, MEAs with varying anode catalyst layer designs will be manufactured and tested in-situ.

2. Results

The introduction of electrically conductive nanofibers as support for iridium catalyst layers is improving in- and through plane conductivity and therefore reducing ohmic resistances as the nanofibers act as electron pathways between the iridium particles but also towards the titanium PTL. Besides improving performance, the manufacturing of MEAs is clearly facilitated. Supported iridium catalysts show stabilizing effects when mixing catalyst inks for e.g. spray coating or casting. Particles are less prone to sediment which results in a more reliable and reproducible fabrication of catalyst layers. Especially when developing low loaded iridium catalyst layers, being able to produce a continuous, homogeneous film with even catalyst distribution is essential. To be able to transfer the advantages of various approaches for supported iridium catalysts to industrial application, the complete production line from catalyst synthesis to MEA fabrication has to be considered.

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